

The Image of the Sandship of the Desert - the Camel in the Stories of Sulayman Ash-Shati

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Annotation: *This article notes that the Persian Gulf (Khaleej Arab countries) has its political, economic importance at the international political level since ancient times, and its geographical location is also of strategic importance. It is also a trade route linking East and West, a branch of the Great Silk Road that stretches along the Persian Gulf and serves as a trade route on the shores of Arab countries. On the one hand, it is devoted to the ships passing through the Gulf, and on the other hand, a camel caravan loaded with goods on a deserted road adjacent to the shore. The article also shows that Suleiman Shotiy, a brilliant representative of Kuwaiti literature from the Arabian Gulf countries, associated images in his works, primarily, with wildlife, a camel, a bay and the coastal world, which found their artistic expression in the stories «Camel».*

Keywords: *Great Silk Road, the Persian Gulf, Suleiman Shotiy, Kuwait, desert, sea, «Camel», East and West, national values, trade road.*

Introduction: A number of Arab states are located on the western shore of the Persian Gulf, which extends from Kuwait in the north to Oman in the south. Here the Gulf connects the Arabian Sea with the Indian Ocean. Such Arab countries as Kuwait, Bahrain, Qatar, Oman and the United Arab Emirates, whose inhabitants are economically and materially prosperous in the entire Arab world, are located on the Arabian Peninsula, and their coasts extend from the Persian Gulf. Therefore, these countries are called the Arab countries located around the Persian Gulf, but the Arabs do not recognize this name, but call them the countries of "al-Khalijah (Gulf)".

This region, despite numerous divisions, is geographically, religiously and historically united. Spiritual and cultural unity is observed in the life of the population of these countries. Researchers and scientists, realizing the historical interconnection of this integrity, this unity, call it in a special way "the cultural lake". From a political and geographical point of view, Khaleej has been of great importance in determining international political and economic criteria since ancient times. Its geographical location is strategic, as it was a trade route connecting the East and the West. We have noticed many references to this in the works of modern writers of the Persian Gulf. The figurative world of the works of one of the brightest representatives of Kuwaiti literature, Suleiman al-Shati, is rich, multifaceted and multi-valued. It is, first of all, an artistic expression of life associated with the world of the desert, camels, sea and coast.

Suleiman al-Shati belongs to the second generation of modern Kuwaiti short story writers. In the 1970s, he quickly entered the literary scene and became known for his realistic stories that depict various aspects of the life of the Kuwaiti people. Thanks to his innate talent, Suleiman al-Shati creates stories with a polished and specific plot, with perfectly drawn images.

The writer's artistic skill is also demonstrated in the fact that he subtly senses changes in time and elegantly expresses the ideological and aesthetic goal of the work.

In his last two collections of short stories, "A Man Who Has Reached a High Rank" and "I Am... Different", Suleiman al-Shati's talent is clearly demonstrated; in these works, he creates his own

unique style that distinguishes him from other short story writers. His style is more complex, he uses new forms of short story writing. The basic writing technique he relies on is that the writer enters the realm of the past from the present, and that the present is the key to unlocking the secrets of this past. The present day (period) is part of a limited history and opens the way to memories by focusing on the past. The writer tries to reveal the purpose of the work, connected with the past, using fragmentation techniques and associative connection methods, briefly dwelling on some situations of the present.

For example, if we take the writer's collection of stories "I am... different" (أنا.. الأخر), we will undoubtedly see the same technique here. The widespread use of the intertextual method by the writer al-Shati in his work of the 80s testifies to his creative stylistic evolution. The intertextual method is widely used in the collection of short stories "I am... another" (أنا.. الأخر). For example, in Suleiman al-Shati's story "The Camel", two places are depicted - the desert and the sea environment. In the story, the father remembers the desert, memories that are very near and dear to his heart. The hero's father grew up in the desert and knows this environment well. It is known that the father who tells this story loves the desert, it is noticeable that when he talks about it, he is worried and worried. The writer says the following about the past life of the inhabitants:

"The people of Khaleej have been struggling with the desert all their lives. The sea is more of a relief from the hardships of the desert for the people of Khaleej, but at the same time, the sea is not a safe place. In fact, the people of Khaleej lived in a difficult and dramatic situation between water and desert, and the question of their life and death was connected with these two worlds. But death in the desert is more open and quiet. And the connection with the sea was based on knowledge and action"

For the writer, the desert is a typical natural environment, albeit dangerous, in which everything is clear. But the writer has a different opinion about the city.

Main part: The story is divided into two parts - the events of the past are reflected retrospectively through the father's memories, and the events of the present day are narrated by the son, who is looking for treatment for his sick father. The categories of past and present tense are not given by a single composition, its parts alternate: present-past-past-present, etc. As for the chronotopic-spatial category, the events take place in different places: in the desert, on the coast, in the city. From the father's story we learn that he came from nomadic Bedouins of the desert, that his family became victims of bloody intertribal conflicts when he was a teenager, and that his mother fled with him from the desert to the sea on a thoroughbred camel, we get acquainted with his life on a coast alien to him. The Bedouin, unaccustomed to coastal life, at first works using his thoroughbred camel and carries heavy loads on it. The huge thoroughbred camel walks with difficulty along the narrow stone streets of the city. After many hardships, a young Bedouin man is forced to sell his camel, which was his soul and heart, his irreplaceable friend, in order to earn a living, and regrets this act for the rest of his life, because the new owner mercilessly uses the camel, loads it with excessively heavy loads and, finally, makes it carry water in large iron tanks. The young Bedouin man watches his camel from the side and is very worried. The animal quickly loses weight, becomes weak and cannot stand on its feet with a heavy load. The angry owner beats and tortures it. At this time, the thoroughbred, docile camel shows its pride and rebels, gathers all its strength to stand up, throws down the load and runs to meet its owner. The owner, who managed to save himself, orders all his servants to drive the camel towards the sea, the camel, entering the sea, falls into the water with all its weight. Dozens of knives cut the camel's body into pieces. The camel dies. The Bedouin regrets selling his camel for the rest of his life. These events took place in Kuwait in the 1950s, when oil money was just starting to flow into the country, life was hard for the Kuwaitis in the desert and on the coast, there was not enough drinking water. The second plot line coincides with the beginning of the 90s, when the Bedouin's son comes of age and takes his sick father abroad for treatment, but he does not recover and seeks a cure in camel milk. The son intends to buy his father a mother camel and another camel similar to his breeding

camel. He meets camel traders in the constituency. They rent out their camels to candidates for parliament, because they artificially create an ancient desert environment around the constituencies in order to get votes: the Bedouins put up yurts and tie the camels to them. By doing so, they show how much they respect traditional values, even if they arrive in these places in expensive Western cars. By this time, when electronic media, television and the Internet were already developed in Kuwait, this shows that the writer had developed a typical postmodern ironic mode in relation to such actions. The writer does not laugh at traditional values, but shows that sometimes turning to them creates paradoxical situations that contradict common sense. The same situation is observed in the story.

"When the city was preparing for the elections, a camel appeared, shaking its head on its long neck in surprise. In its eyes was a sign of a thousand-year-old sadness. Perhaps it was remembering the events of the previous month. Something strange happened to it this month. They wrapped it in a thick rope and put it in a truck, then lowered it in front of a yurt and tied it. After a couple of days, it noticed that they were taking care of it differently, trying to show it off and attract the attention of those around it. The following days passed in the same way, it was driven from place to place and put on display".

The camel seller began to praise his goods. Then the future deputy tells why he rents a camel.

"-Stop! Don't praise it too much. Who told you that I'm interested in all this? I just want its shape. Do you think I'm going to ride it or eat it?"

The seller immediately understood the purpose:

"Whoever used it was blessed, and the votes for it were higher in the previous elections."

The writer's thoughts about the elections were included in the plot of the story, and the social retreat occurred through the hero's internal monologue. It reflects the country's attitude to the elections, the role of subjective factors in the elections and the possibility that a person can change his mind during the voting process, even if he previously held a different opinion. In the image of one of the main characters of Suleiman al-Shati's story "Camel" - in the image of the father - we see a sign of sadness, sadness towards the city, which indicates that many values have been lost in the city and there is disunity among people, that freedom is limited, that the life of the city's people is unblessed and unhappy (the actions of the candidates in the elections, their empty talk, etc.).

Analyzing the story, along with the unique plot lines and compositional structure, intertextuality and ironic mode, we drew attention to another aspect of the story: the artistic speech of the story is distinguished by its expressiveness and abundance of poetic expressions.

Here is a description of the tribal a thoroughbred camel. He saves the boy from tribal strife, bloody revenge and executions and carries him across the desert:

"He is like a ship, smoothly floating in the water. The further we went into the desert, the higher my camel became, straightening its frame, like a huge statue. His steps are firm, his legs are like pillars rising from the earth or falling from the sky. His broad chest seems to break through his competitors in competitions. He proudly raised his strong head, as if pleased with what he saw, radiating confidence and peace. Ahead are endless horizons, and behind are terrible conflicts, anger and inflamed, unhealed wounds.

This is a hymn to the camel. It feels like a national spirit! The description of the camel is similar to the description of the camel in jahiliyya and classical Arabic poetry! This attribute is a continuation of this tradition in modern literature! In the Arabic text one can discern poetry and even worship. Such generalization and compactness of thought is often found in classical Arabic literature in the genres of

"adab", "maqoma", "edifying story", "khitaba", and in this regard, the continuation of the same classical tradition can be seen in the use of aphorisms in the story of Suleiman al-Shati.

In general, the writers of Khalij have a complex relationship with the city - on the one hand, they are surprised to see changes, expansions, decorations in it, and on the other - they see many vices in it, and dwell on village life, remember the old days, and indulge in memories, and this often finds its expression in retrospect.

But this can also be called a display of a romantic mood, because in our opinion, no one thinks about a real return to the past, to the hard life in the village. The cult of the old desert life is nothing more than a protest against loneliness, isolation and other social ills of the big city.

In conclusion, it can be said that in updating the forms of stories of the Arab countries of Khaliya, expanding the range of themes, the coherence of images and means of expression associated with the desert, camels, the sea and coastal world, Suleiman al-Shati shows not only national social situations, but also introduces a unique new way of perceiving a person based on universal human values.

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